

Systems Thinking Approach to Transform Individual's Mindset and Identity to Improve Innovation Performance and Organizational Engagement: An Action Research Study in Minlong Ceramic Art Museum in China

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Abstract:- This action research study explored the individual's Open-mindedness (OM) and Identity (ID) to have an impact on the effect of innovation performance (IP) and employee organization engagement (OE) at a cultural and creative enterprise by using Peter Senge's systems thinking process as a blueprint for organizational development interventions (ODIs). The research sample consists of 4 leaders and 26 employees. The researcher used the mixed method with a survey questionnaires instrument of 22 items. Cronbach alpha reliability test result was 0.914, and the IOC content validity test result was more significant than 0.6 for each item. The researcher evaluated data with the Shapiro-Wilk test and found data were not normally distributed. The study findings are of statistical significance due to the p-value of the hypothesis being less than 0.05 as shown, (1) after pre- and post-ODI, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test analysis, H1a has $OM_p=0.001$; H2a has $ID_p=0.008$, H3a has $IP_p=0.007$; H4a has $OE_p=0.006$, so there is a statistically significant difference on OM, ID, IP and OE before and after ODI. (2) Spearman rank Correlation Test was applied, and H5a has $P=0.001$; H6a has $P=0.03$; H7a has $P=0.000$; H8a has $P=0.000$, so there is a statistically significant relationship between OM and IP, ID and IP, OM and OE, ID, and OE. (3) Ordinal logistic regression Analyses were applied. H9a has OM and ID on $IPP=0.000$; H10a has OM and ID on $OEP=0.000$, so there is a statistically significant effect that OM and ID have an impact on IP; OM and ID have an impact on OE. Based on Qualitative findings: after pre- and post-ODI, eight out of ten employees mentioned that more communication and cooperative behaviors were generated among employees. This evidence supports H1a. Nine out of ten employees said that they felt work was meaningful and fulfilling. This evidence supports H2a. The new projects, such as the Winter Olympics, the cultural program at the Forbidden City, and the improved financial results in the first quarter of 2022. This evidence supports H3a. Seven out of ten employees mentioned that they devoted more time to work. This evidence supports H4a. Interview and observation found that OM and ID can improve IP and OE, respectively. This evidence supports H5a to H8a. Eight of ten employees said that promoting OM and ID increases new business and generates more work

initiative and enthusiasm. This evidence supports H9a and H10a.

Keywords:- Cultural and creative industry; systems thinking; open-mindedness; identity; innovation performance; organizational engagement.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the in-depth development of the knowledge and information economy, CCI has become a prominent growth point for world economic growth. The CCI has brought massive wealth to many countries and promoted the widespread dissemination of ideas. The concept of CCI first appeared in Australia in 1994 [1]. The UK was one of the first countries to implement the CCI idea and introduce related policies. In 1997, the creative industry was identified as the main driving force and source of future economic growth [2].

China's long history and profound cultural background did not provide many advantages to its industrialization process. As China's capital and political and cultural center, Beijing's economic solid foundation and the rapid development of CCI have played an essential role in enhancing Beijing's comprehensive capabilities. The 13th Five-Year Plan period is necessary for economic transformation. When faced with the new situation of the "coordinated development" of the Belt and Road Initiative, the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region, and Beijing's capital functional organizations, the development of Beijing's CCI needs breakthroughs and to continuously optimize its layout, promote industrial integration, highlight regional characteristics, and strive to achieve the goal of the more excellent added value of the CCI in GDP.

This dissertation attempts to use the case of Beijing cultural and creative enterprises-the problems faced by the organizational development of MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum, to conduct an in-depth study on the factors that hinder the organizational development of CCI enterprises and to explore their open-mindedness, identity, and innovation performance, The article also aims at providing recommendations for the development of other CCI organizations in Beijing, and research ideas for issues related to the development of CCI.

Along with the social and economic development and citizens' increasingly diversified spiritual and cultural life, cultural demand and consumption have brought remarkable growth. This situation provides tremendous potential for the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum's development. In addition, with a daily increase in the ceramic art museum experience, including ceramic design and private customs, more aesthetic demand demonstrates its rapid development. The company should also have higher employee requirements from skills and customer service perspectives. In conclusion, they face ever-increasing development opportunities and play an increasingly important role in the cultural field. The researcher used the SWOT analysis to evaluate the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum and clarify the organization's current strengths, problems, opportunities, challenges, and future development directions. On the one hand, the role of the researcher in this study was that of a participant-observer. Working with the participants on the project and, in the process, becoming an observer simultaneously. Observed other activities and conducted interviews while participating in the project activities. SWOT analysis summary: 1. The current state of lack of teamwork and internal competition is not suitable for the development of MAM. 2. MAM needs a set of effective methods to improve employees' OM, ID, IP, and OE.

A. The Rationale For Choosing Peter Senge's Fifth Disciplines As A Blueprint for Odis In This Study

Senge[3] merges the concept of systems thinking into organizational learning, integrating the five elements into a comprehensive system of theory and practice. It is based on actual thinking. The five disciplines are shared vision, mental modeling, personal proficiency, team learning, and system thinking. Among these are systems thinking from MIT Systems Dynamics Group, organizational learning theory from the work of Argyris and Schein, and creative tension from the work of Robert Fritz, all of which have influenced the establishment of Senge's theory[4]. One of the most important disciplines is systems thinking. The soul of a learning organization is personal proficiency, and the foundation of a learning organization is team learning. Systems thinking is a discipline that has a holistic perspective. To see the interconnectedness of things rather than just seeing things, to see the changing state of physical objects rather than just the current stopped state, it is the discipline of seeing the complex structure of things that supports the causes. Systems thinking adjusts the way of thinking and gives us a new tool to understand the world[5]. Personal proficiency helps people by reinforcing their unique visions and strengthening their abilities by fulfilling their inner desires. Mental models help people understand what they observe and improve their abilities by constantly interacting with others. A shared vision empowers people by generating a common goal and makes people's goals clearer and more determined. Team learning strengthens the collective ability to learn and interact, creating empathy and synergy in learning. Systems thinking allows people to recognize the interconnectedness of things, generating better perspectives and solutions to problems [6].

Mindset reflects the thinking and behaviors of employees. The mindset of an individual is very influential, and managers and researchers need to understand how this concept manifests itself in the daily conduct of employees. Most people have basic mental models that can form the basic view of how to approach things. Such patterns can explain, interpret, and predict behaviors[7]. Transformation in this study refers to changing employees' mindsets from one form to another. This study provides new and deeper insights into the shift in the mindset of employees in companies and how employees respond to the transformation. The study examines the changing process of employees' mindsets throughout the change.

Senge's research recommends learning to transform human mindsets and mental models. A systemic perspective is needed to achieve corporate vision and performance goals. The mind, heart, and hands are necessary for sustainable corporation and organizational development, especially with spirituality, mental models, systems thinking, foresight, and a sustainable mindset. Senge's Fifth Discipline research on learning organizations shows a positive relationship between learning organizations and empowerment, organizational participation, performance, productivity, and leadership. Senge's view of the learning organization is compatible with the systems thinking method, which can change employees' thinking and engagement.

B. Research Problem

This action research study intends to identify causes (mindset, identity) to improve innovative performance and employees' engagement of MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum, taking Peter Senge's system thinking process as a blueprint for organization development interventions (ODIs).

C. Research Objectives

- To identify the current situation of open-mindedness, identity, employees' innovative performance, and organizational engagement.
- To identify and design the organization development interventions (ODIs) to develop open-mindedness and identity.
- To identify the difference between pre-and post-ODI on open-mindedness, Identity, Innovation performance, and organizational Engagement Intention.
- To examine the impact of open-mindedness and identity on the employees' innovation performance.
- To examine the impact of open-mindedness and identity on the employees' organizational engagement.

This case study aims to solve MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum's critical issues in practice, such as IP and OE, using the ODI (Peter Senge's systems thinking process). The practice of MINLONG Group can be used as an example to provide a reference for other cultural and creative industry enterprises in Beijing.

D. Literature review

The innovation of organizational members is the basis of organizational innovation, and organizational innovation occurs when individual innovation reaches the organizational level [8]. Organizational innovation requires transforming individual innovation performance and individual participation in the organization. Therefore, the researcher reviews this study's open-mindedness, innovation performance, identification, and organizational engagement.

II. KEY RESEARCH AREAS IN OPEN-MINDEDNESS; IDENTITY; INNOVATION PERFORMANCE, AND ORGANIZATIONAL ENGAGEMENT

A. Open-mindedness

Open-mindedness is "an intellectual virtue that manifests in a willingness to form and revise our ideas in light of a critical examination of evidence and arguments to achieve the elusive ideals of objectivity and impartiality. One notable aspect of the discussion around open-mindedness challenges the coherence of the idea that one can be open-minded while having strong (or "intense") beliefs. First, openness as an educational goal can be abandoned; second, the contradiction can be reconciled by distinguishing between openness to something and openness as a disposition [9]. Open-mindedness is suitable for truth. If openness is associated with reality, which is contingent, and if the necessary association with truth is what makes an intellectual virtue a virtue, then the status of openness as an intellectual virtue is jeopardized[10]. Existing research derives the moral value of openness from the epistemological role it plays in ethical thought. Open-mindedness as a moral virtue promotes our flourishing with others in a way that is entirely unrelated to the role of correcting our beliefs[11]. Reflections on the integrity of open-mindedness demonstrate that religious ethics can help make spiritual life more humane in a liberal, secular context [12]. The relationship between the concept of essential open-mindedness and previous claims about open-mindedness, as well as the differences between the two, have been examined in previous research [13].

B. Identity

Social identity theory is an interactionist social psychological theory that deals with the role of self-perception and related cognitive processes as well as social beliefs in group processes and intergroup relations. It is primarily used to explain intergroup relations [14]. The social identity approach in psychology addresses the concept of group identity and its impact on the self and relationships with others. Some critical extensions and developments of the social identity approach have focused on contextual factors that can influence the salience and strategic expression of identity and the importance of emotions to group identity and group life [15]. One of the most effective ways to reduce self-uncertainty is through self-categorization for group identification. Group identification reduces tension because it allows people to internalize a shared identity and associated group archetypes. Internal states, such as attitudes, feelings, and emotions, are often shared among group members. Self-uncertainty motivates

people to establish a shared reality through group identity[16]. Group archetypal leaders are more supported and trusted than non-archetypal leaders and are perceived by members as more effective leaders, especially when group membership is a central and salient aspect of membership and when members identify strongly with the group[17].

C. Innovation performance

Innovation has long been recognized as an essential factor in creating and maintaining the competitiveness of countries and firms. Introducing innovation, especially product innovation, is a critical driver of export intensity. The impact of innovation on exports is considerable[18]. Firm innovation and export behavior are mutually driven processes. In both directions, the impact of product innovation is quantitatively more significant than other forms of creation. Self-selection of innovation activities by exporting firms explicitly considers the firm's strategic and investment decisions. Innovation and export activities are products of different strategies, while the firm's investment in worker training and IT capital increases the likelihood of innovation[19]. There is extensive literature on the factors that influence innovation performance but little on the impact of an economy's knowledge base on innovation performance. An empirical study verifies that the knowledge base, expressed as a triple helix relationship of "technology, organization, and geography," positively influences innovation performance [20]. Firms benefit from the more intense competition in international markets, forcing them to intensify their innovation activities. In addition to the drivers of innovation performance, there are external factors that have an impact on a firm's innovation performance. These factors may come from a firm and industry characteristics, such as size, age, technological antagonism, etc.[21].

D. Organizational engagement

Kahn [22] described engagement as a mental state of positive behavior at work. Similarly, engagement is a crucial driver of personal attitudes, behaviors, performance, organizational performance, and productivity [23]. In addition, internal communication, rewards, and recognition are significantly related to employee engagement. In addition to work-life balance, employee engagement is unignorable in the performance of textile employees [24]. Changes in management practices that increase employee engagement can improve organizational performance [25]. High-potential employees participating in leadership development activities can enhance their work engagement[26]. In recent years, employee engagement has become a hot topic of discussion in popular business media and consulting firms. The case has attracted the interest of various stakeholder groups, ranging from academic HR practitioners to policymakers or government agencies [27]. Scholars and practitioners agree that employee engagement positively impacts individual and organizational performance. The three dimensions of employee engagement - congruence, affectivity, and action orientation - are presented in an understandable form and language that allows practitioners to look more closely at crucial engagement elements that align with the organization's human capital strategy and contribute to performance

[28].Employees' engagement was negatively associated with lagged measures of turnover intentions and deviant work behaviors against the organization. The results suggest that perceived organizational support moderates the relationship between work engagement and turnover intentions and

abnormal behavior toward the organization, such that perceived organizational support compensates for relatively low work engagement[29]. Meaningful work is an essential predictor, and managers can develop efforts that allow employees to connect their purpose to their work [30].

III. CONCEPTUAL RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed by the author for this study

The conceptual framework of this research is shown in Figure. The fifth discipline[31] is an essential basic concept of this research and discusses the relationship between variables. According to literature research, the purpose of the Fifth Discipline is to make the organization's overall performance more significant than the result of each part of the organization added together. Senge's LO theory starts from shaping employees' mindsets and competencies and integrates organizational goals with the shaping of individuals so that individual goals are aligned with organizational goals. Meanwhile, Senge's [32] LO theory elucidates effective forms of organizational structure. In this study, the researchers aim to examine the effects of the change in innovation performance and engagement on the employees.

The independent variables are open-mindedness and identity, whose factors and developments influence positive changes in behavior that lead to higher organizational performance. Innovation performance and organizational engagement are identified as dependent variables.

IV. METHOD

A. The model of the study

After studying the model of Peter M. Senge's Fifth Discipline and combining it with the organizational development process of the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum, the researcher proposes an organizational development model based on cultural and creative industry enterprises, as shown in Figure.

Fig. 2: System Thinking Approach to Transforming an Individual's Mindset and Identity to Improve Innovation Performance and Organizational Engagement

The researchers suggest that systematic thinking is placed at the center, while personal mastery, mental model, shared vision, and organizational learning form an organic integration., there is a particular order of logical relationships. The transformation from self-transcendence to team learning constitutes a gradual progression, while system thinking provides guiding ideas, principles, and techniques for establishing a learning organization. Systematic review fuses the first four disciplines into a unified body of theory and practice. Systematic thinking is the soul of a learning organization. It provides a rational brain, a perfect way of thinking, individual learning, team learning, reviewing the mind, and establishing a vision. It is all because systems thinking influences achieving organizational goals.

Based on the results of observation and interviews in the study, four relevant variables in this study are outlined, including OM, ID, IP, and OE, which are derived from the actual problems faced by enterprises and can correspond to the model of the Fifth Discipline, where IP corresponds to Personal Mastery. OM corresponds to the Mental Models. The ID corresponds to Shared Vision. Establishing a shared vision impacts the formation of corporate values. Employees can stimulate OE and IP improvement based on their ID. OE corresponds to team learning. The formation of groups strengthens organizational members' beliefs, thereby increasing employees' OE.

Also, the correlations between variables and the changes before and after ODI were verified to enhance employees' open-mindedness, identity, innovative performance, and organizational engagement through a systemic thinking intervention approach. Specific interventions include in-depth talks, workshops, team building, and group activities that organically integrate the variables into this study and the concepts in the Fifth Discipline to form the model.

B. Population and sample

All participants are selected from the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum (focal organization). Participants in the study include 4 leaders and 26 employees. All team members are from MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum. It is divided into four departments: Master Workshop, Ceramic Bar, Ceramic Teaching and Research Group, and Marketing Department. The MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum is responsible for teaching, product development, creation, marketing, and other tasks. The age of the leaders is between 40 and 60 years old. All employees are between 20 and 60 years old. All participants have a bachelor's degree or above in fine arts or arts and craft artist qualification.

In the quantitative research, all MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum employees were selected to participate in the study, including 26 employees. Four team leaders were interviewed in qualitative research, two provincial inheritors of intangible cultural heritage, and 40% of team members received selective interviews.

C. Instruments

In this study, mixed research methods are used. This study uses a mixed research approach of open-mindedness, identity, innovation performance, and organizational engagement. This research starts with a case study of cultural and creative industry organizations, which adapt to the characteristics of cultural and creative industry enterprises. It completes a questionnaire survey based on a literature review. All items in the questionnaire use a Likert five-point scale. There are three reverse questions in the 22 items of the questionnaire to test whether the respondent has answered each question carefully. The answers to the questions will be reversed in the data processing after the data collection is completed.

The measurement of open-mindedness refers to the scales used by Dean Tjosvold et al. [33]. The researchers modified the related content to adapt to the content and background of the study, including comments such as "I consider the ideas of the other open-mindedly" and "I understand what my colleagues are trying to accomplish." The identity measurement refers to the scales used by Simon et al. [34]. The researchers modify the related content to adapt to the content and background of the study, including "I see myself as a member of this group" and "I am not overly concerned about how others view our organization." The measurement of innovation performance refers to the scales used by Prajogo and Ahmed [35]. The researchers modify the related content to adapt to the content and background of the study, including "I can actively support innovative ideas" and "I can translate innovative ideas into practical applications." The measurement of organization engagement refers to the scales Schaufeli et al. [36] used. The researchers modify the related content to adapt to the content and background of the study, including "I feel I am in a purposeful and meaningful job." And "I am passionate about my work."

D. Instruments' validity and reliability for quantitative data

The researchers conducted an item objective congruence (IOC) test validity. The researchers invited five experts to participate in the IOC test. In the OD field, two professors are from China and the United States. One is from China, a professor of management, another is the director of the student office of the university, and the last is the deputy secretary of the School of Art and Design. After testing, the validity of each item in the questionnaire is greater than or equal to 0.6. Therefore, the questionnaire is valid.

To test reliability, the researcher conducted one pilot study with a sample size of = 23. In this paper, internal reliability analysis tests each scale item's internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is used to evaluate the internal consistency. The test was conducted at Perfect World Co., Ltd. Perfect World Co., Ltd is a cultural and creative industry company. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of this subject is 0.914, indicating that the acceptable range is substantial. The results prove the reliability of the questionnaire.

E. Data analysis

First, the quantitative data are collected from the two surveys, pre-ODI and post-ODI. The SPSS program is used as a computing tool for the data analysis in this study using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) program. First, the researcher checks whether the data is normally distributed. The number of respondents is small (N=26), less than 50. Researchers tend to check the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test (S-W test) for normality and suppose the P-value of the significance test obtained using the S-W test is more significant than 0.05. In that case, it indicates that this data group meets normal distribution. Tests Hypotheses 1- 4 using Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test. Suppose the p-values of the pair are less than .05 (at a 95% Confidence Interval of the Difference). Test hypotheses 5- 8, Spearman rank Correlation Test. If the value $r = 1$ means a perfect positive correlation and $r = -1$ means a perfect negative correlation. Ordinal logistic regression analysis was performed on the variables to test hypotheses 9-10. if the P-value is less than 0.05, hypotheses 90 and 100 are rejected.

F. Procedures

In turn, alternative hypotheses 5a and 6a are accepted. The R-squared value of the model (McFadden R-squared) can represent the percentage of the dependent variable that the independent variable can explain.

Qualitative data analysis is a content analysis based on the qualitative data collected in interviews. In this analysis, the contents of pre-and post-ODI are compared and analyzed. These analyses include 1) whether employees open their minds; 2) whether employees develop an identity; 3) whether the employee's performance has been improved after ODI, and 4) whether there is an impact of change on their innovation performance and organizational engagement. This article introduces content analysis to analyze a large amount of text information. To sum up, the researcher has systematically analyzed and compared the data collected in different quantitative and qualitative ways to meet the research questions and hypotheses proposed in the previous chapter.

Fig. 3: Action Research Framework

Source: Developed by the author for this study

G. Pre-ODI stage

The researcher used tools to collect data from participants. When analysis starts, two research methods are used: quantitative and qualitative, namely the mix-method. The pre-ODI phase lasts two weeks before the start of the ODI phase. Researchers use quantitative methods to collect independent and dependent variable data and analyze participants' current open-mindedness, identity, organizational performance, and engagement level. The final purpose of collecting quantitative data in the pre-ODI stage is to test employees' present independent variables and dependent variable status. The Researcher use interview methods to collect team leaders' opinions and employees' feelings which include which aspect of innovation performance does well or less well; what they intend to do more of; how they feel about the current level of employee engagement, and what problems do they think there are in this regard.

When all the data collected in the pre-ODI phase is completed, it is used for the measurement after ODI for comparison. In this process, minimizing the interference and impact on the post-test data is necessary. Therefore, the results will not be directly fed back to the participants. However, specific analysis and reflections will be carried out to clarify the potential problem further. It is better to adjust for the following intervention process.

H. Post-ODI phase

The ODI activities were carried out from September 2021 - to October 2021. As designed during the ODI phase, the change process follows the Fifth Discipline discussed earlier. Peter Senge's book, Systems thinking, is a conceptual framework, a body of knowledge, and a series of tools to help people learn and understand knowledge[37]. Senge [38] considered systems thinking to look at the world holistically. Systems thinking leads to the realization that

each event impacts the others. Only by carefully considering the pattern can the whole system be understood.

At the workshop, facilitators first let participants understand the role and significance of system thinking through case studies and then realize the importance of systems thinking for life and career development. The facilitator first makes the participants understand that System thinking is not a critical technology. Still, people must first change their mentality and complete the thinking and perception learning process. System thinking, as a way of thinking and research tool, must follow some basic principles. As a means of system thinking, many authors have done much research. The focus is on learning organizational strategies and active countermeasures to cultivate new ways of thinking and achieve desired achievements [39].

Group Dynamic Workshop is done through in-depth discussions, in which everyone shares their most impressive and proud moments. This process brings everyone closer to each other. It allows participants to see things with new eyes, responds objectively to data and facts, and build a field that can flow naturally. More ideas and creative ideas are generated through this process, and a consensus shall finally be achieved. Team building led to building a shared vision and improving employee initiative and willingness to work. Creating a shared vision reconciles differences, and the team learning process reconciles differences into motivation, stimulating everyone's wisdom and shaping a shared vision. Therefore, the process should start with team learning, training the learning ability of the organization, and then the expert in the principles and methods of cooperative and organizational learning, which will form a more efficient organization.

I. Post-ODI phase

The post-ODI stage aims to check for changes in the employees' innovation performance level and organizational engagement after ODI. For another data collection, all team members and leaders will use the same tools in the pre-ODI stage. The research subjects are the previous group, the same leaders, and team members. The post-ODI phase is carried out immediately after the ODI phase, including collecting and analyzing data, which takes two weeks.

In the post-ODI stage, a specific and detailed comparative analysis will be carried out with the data of the pre-ODI to find out the differences and changes and, on this basis, to verify whether the research problem has been solved and whether the proposed hypothesis can be tested. At the same time, the researchers reflect on the entire research process and give feedback to the organization's leadership to promote change to the next round of action research.

J. Demographic profiles

All participants were selected from the MINLONG Ceramic Museum (key organization). Participants in the study include four leaders and 26 employees. The research focuses on the employee level, aiming to improve employees' mentality, innovation performance, and work engagement through systematic thinking and intervention methods. All team members are from MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum. The museum is divided into four departments: Master Workshop, Ceramic rod, Ceramic Teaching, Research Group, and Marketing Department. MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum is a cultural creative industry enterprise. Its main business includes ceramic art teaching, product development, creation, market transformation, marketing, and other aspects of work.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	14	53.85%
Female	12	46.15%

Table 1: Gender profile of the study

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Under 25	7	26.92%
25- 34	12	46.15%
35- 44	5	19.23%
45- 55	1	3.85%
Over 55	1	3.85%

Table 2: Age profile of the study

Education level	Frequency	Percentage
High school or below	3	11.54%
Junior college degree	10	38.46%
Bachelor's degree	13	50%
Total	26	100%

Table 3: Education Level Profile of the Study

Working years	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	8	30.77%
3-5 years	5	19.23%
5-10 years	7	26.92%
10-20 years	4	15.38%
More than 20 years	2	7.69%
Total	26	100%

Table 4: Working Years Profile of the Study

K. The first objective was to identify the current situation of open-mindedness, identity, employees' innovative performance, and organizational engagement.

The status of the target organization was assessed through the SWOT analysis method in the pre-ODIs phase. Quantitative and qualitative tools were also used to explore the participants' perceptions.

A SWOT assessment helped researchers reveal the key issues affecting the current business performance and operations of the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum. The MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum team has many years of creative background and practical experience in the arts. Its long-term projects of cultural communication and exhibition display have accumulated a good reputation for the organization. However, the traditional business has been dramatically impacted due to the epidemic. The organizations' businesses have seen a significant decline due to the cultural and creative industry characteristics, including staff's lack of collaboration, which hinders innovative performance. While according to the organization's leadership, the level of organizational commitment of employees needs improvement. The development of the Internet economy and new communication formats provides opportunities for organizations to expand their business in new directions. To seize these upcoming opportunities, team performance needs to be improved by raising the level of creative performance and increasing the organizational engagement of employees. On the other hand, the impact of the epidemic and the transformation and upgrading of the cultural and creative industries present significant challenges on multiple fronts. Team development at the MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum can enhance the organization's competitiveness.

Quantitative data analysis was used to measure employees' open-mindedness, identity, innovation performance, and organizational engagement before ODI. The data were considered to belong to a non-normal distribution state by the one-sample K-s normality test. Thus, the statistical method of the non-parametric test was used. The median was taken in the statistics to calculate the median.

These quantitative findings are consistently supported by the qualitative data obtained from interviews with managers and employees. Employees primarily work independently of each other. The level of communication and teamwork between managers and employees and that within employees in the development and creation of business is low, affecting employees' innovative performance and organizational involvement. In addition,

employees do not have enough sense of identity with the team or the individual. They do not have enough awareness of being an individual in the whole work process, and employees usually do not go beyond their job responsibilities to support each other.

Through observation, we can find that employees are more competitive than collaborative in their work, which is fine for individual creativity. Still, the overall team performance and project advancement will be affected. The lack of organizational support felt by team members in their work is another negative factor. For these reasons, employees' innovation performance and organizational engagement are insufficient.

L. The second objective was to identify and design the organization development interventions (ODIs) to develop open-mindedness and identity.

This action research is modeled on Peter M. Senge's Fifth Discipline. It sets the research context for developing and implementing a series of ODIs for MINLONG Ceramic Art Museum employees based on a quantitative analysis of the Pre and Post ODI phases. Based on SWOT analysis and Pre ODI quantitative and qualitative data, while considering the target company's culture and context, the researcher applies organizational development interventions to change the open-mindedness, identity, innovation performance, and level of organizational engagement of members of the firm. Systems thinking workshops focus on helping team members to be able to see things from different perspectives and grasp the nature of systems thinking. And training sessions help employees to acquire systems thinking skills through practice. The ODI process helps to promote learning by reinforcing open-mindedness and identity, which increases collaboration and communication at work. Thus, the four variables of employee open-mindedness, identity, innovation performance, and employee organizational engagement have been significantly improved during the Post ODI phase.

M. The third objective was to identify the difference between Pre- and Post-ODI on open-mindedness, Identity, Innovation performance, and organizational engagement Intention.

Research hypotheses H1-H4 are consistent with research objective three, read as follows.

Hypothesis 1

H10: Open-mindedness has no statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

H1a: Open-mindedness has a statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

Hypothesis 2

H20: Identity has no statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

H2a: Identity has a statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

Hypothesis 3

H30: Innovation performance has no statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

H3a: Innovation performance has a statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

Hypothesis 4

H40: Organizational engagement has no statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

H4a: Organizational engagement has a statistically significant difference between Pre-ODI and Post-ODI.

Variable	Number	Sig.	Result
OM Post-OM Pre	26	0.001	Reject null hypothesis
ID Post-ID Pre	26	0.008	Reject null hypothesis
IP Post-IP Pre	26	0.007	Reject null hypothesis
OE Post-OE Pre	26	0.006	Reject null hypothesis

Table 5: Test Results of the Third Objective

*P≤0.05;

OM: Open-mindedness (H7), ID: Identity (H8); IP: Innovative Performance(H9); OE: Organization Engagement(H10)

The researcher tested H1, H2, H3, and H4 with a Wilcoxon signed-rank test for differences in the change before and after the OD intervention; the results showed that all the p-values were less than 0.05. Thus H10, H20, H30, and H40 were rejected, and H1a, H2a, H3a, and H4a were accepted.

The above test statistics show a significant difference between the post-ODI and pre-ODI medians. The post-ODI median is higher than the pre-ODI median. The result indicates that ODI strengthened organizational employees' open-mindedness and identity; thus, innovation performance and engagement improved.

N. The fourth objective was to examine the impact of open-mindedness and identity on the employees' innovation performance.

Research hypotheses H5, H6, and H9, are consistent with study objective three and read as follows:

Hypothesis 5

H50: Open-mindedness has no statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

H5a: Open-mindedness has a statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

Hypothesis 6

H60: Identity has no statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

H6a: Identity has a statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

Hypothesis 9

H90: Open-mindedness and Identity have no statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

H9a: Open-mindedness and Identity have a statistically significant impact on innovation performance.

Variable	Number	Correlation Coefficient	Sig.	Result
OM-IP	26	0.601	0.001	Reject null hypothesis
ID-IP	26	0.555	0.003	Reject null hypothesis

Table 6: Test Results of the Fourth Objective

*P≤0.05

OM: Open-mindedness, ID: Identity; IP: Innovative Performance; OE: Organization Engagement

H5 and H6 used the Spearman correlation test to detect the correlation of the variables, and the p-values were less than 0.05, thus rejecting H50-H60 and choosing the alternative hypothesis.

Variable	Number	McFadden	Sig.	Result
OM, ID-IP	26	0.771	0.000	Reject null hypothesis

Table 7: Test Results of The Fourth Objective

*P≤0.05

OM: Open-mindedness, ID: Identity; IP: Innovative Performance; OE: Organization Engagement

H9 used ordered logistic regression to test the degree of influence of the variables, and all p-values were less than 0.05, thus rejecting H90 and choosing the alternative hypothesis.

The results of the qualitative studies can also support these quantitative studies, and the post-ODI interviews reveal that an open-minded employee could provide more communication and help. Both quantitative and qualitative data analysis showed that an open mind makes change and improvement possible. Thus, open-mindedness can be considered a prerequisite and necessary foundation for improving employee performance in a company.

The same results indicate that employee identification is essential for improving innovation performance. It is considered a vital factor for the development of innovation performance in this study.

Through the ODI process, the organization acquired more projects based on the organization's new initiatives with more employee input. With the team's joint participation and collaboration, the organization's first-quarter financial results improved significantly compared with the last quarter of last year while undertaking large cultural production projects such as the production of ceramic companion gifts for the Beijing Winter Olympics in

Zhangjiakou city and the ceramic culture course at the Forbidden City Museum.

O. The fifth objective was to examine the impact of open-mindedness and identity on the employees' organizational engagement.

Research hypotheses H7, H8, and H10, are consistent with research objective four and read as follows.

Hypothesis 7

H70: Open-mindedness has no statistically significant impact on organizational engagement.

H7a: Open-mindedness has a statistically significant impact on organizational engagement.

Hypothesis 8

H80: Identity has no statistically significant impact on organizational engagement.

H8a: Identity has a statistically significant impact on organizational engagement.

Hypothesis 10

H100: Open-mindedness and Identity have no statistically significant impact on Organization engagement.

H10a: Open-mindedness and Identity have a statistically significant impact on Organization engagement.

Variable	Number	Correlation Coefficient	Sig.	Result
OM-OE	26	0.794	0.000	Reject null hypothesis
ID-OE	26	0.685	0.000	Reject null hypothesis

Table 8: Test Results of the Fifth Objective

*P≤0.05

OM: Open-mindedness, ID: Identity; IP: Innovative Performance; OE: Organization Engagement

H7 and H8 used the Spearman correlation test to detect the correlation of the variables, and the p-values were less than 0.05, thus rejecting H70, and H80 and choosing the alternative hypothesis.

Variable	Number	McFadden	Sig.	Result
OM, ID-OE	26	0.861	0.000	Reject null hypothesis

Table 9: Test Results of the Fifth Objective

*P≤0.05

OM: Open-mindedness, ID: Identity; OE: Organization Engagement

H10 used ordered logistic regression to test the degree of influence of the variables, and all p-values were less than 0.05, thus rejecting H100 and choosing the alternative hypothesis.

In qualitative data analysis, identity is another area many team leaders want to nurture and improve. In the post-ODI interviews, most of them indicate that they want to do more to create a sense of identity among their employees. They realize that praising and affirming their values

strengthen employees' sense of identity, which helps increase organizational engagement. On the flip side, employees want to derive satisfaction and fulfillment from their role orientation. At the same time, an enhanced organizational identity can further motivate and strengthen employees' organizational engagement, giving them a greater desire to work and participate proactively.

After the ODI, in the project of ceramic culture course production of the Palace Museum, the first phase to do 20

episodes of the course, many people volunteered to take on the main task in the production process. In the final determination of the best mission, from 60-year-old teachers to 20-year-old college students have volunteered to take on the job. The filming often lasts from 7-8 p.m., so the staff's active participation and organizational involvement have significantly been elevated. A comparative content analysis was used to analyze interview data. Similar patterns and themes were found before and after the ODIs. The qualitative analysis supports positive improvements in open-mindedness, identity, innovative performance, and organizational engagement of the company's employees. Based on the post-ODI interviews, nine team members revealed the initial impact of the systematic thinking intervention on open-mindedness, identity, innovation performance, and organizational engagement.

In summary, employees can perceive enhancements in multiple ways after ODIs, which can positively influence their innovative performance and competency development. However, in the researcher's opinion, the team members revealed in the interviews that they would prefer a deeper, more sustained, and somehow institutionalized impact. Although the above findings suggest that team members disclosed the initial impact, in the researchers' opinion, this issue needs further ODI process for more results. As practitioners in the cultural and creative industries, based on their previous experiences, many of their work and creations are in an independent state, lacking experience in cooperation and collaboration. They are not as good as practitioners in other industries in terms of open-mindedness and identity. Therefore, they need more time to learn, practice, get feedback, relearn, and practice again rigorously before they can begin to develop and change themselves to impact their creative performance. Therefore, this study reveals only preliminary findings regarding the impact of change.

V. DISCUSSION

This case study aims to solve MAM's critical issues in practice, such as IP and OE, using the ODI (Peter Senge's systems thinking process). The starting point of this study is the problem. Through observation and participation in the project, the researcher identified several issues in MAM's organizational development that are closely related to the nature of the employees' work. As art practitioners, most creative activities are in an independent state, which conflicts with the organization's performance, and the lack of collaboration and communication hinders the achievement of innovative performance of the organization.

Through in-depth communication with the CEO, the problems faced by employees are identified and addressed from the employees' perspective. The first step is to have a holistic view of the employees' work and organizational identity and to use the systems thinking approach in the Fifth Discipline to enhance the employees' open mind and organizational identity to improve their engagement and innovation performance. The study found that the results show that employees' open-mindedness and identity can positively influence organizational engagement and

innovation performance. And solve the difficulties faced by the organization.

It should be noted that the sample size from one cultural and creative enterprise is limited, and further research in this direction needs an enormous research scope. Still, it can also be found that because of the independent nature of cultural and creative activities themselves, the results of this study are somewhat general and can be used as a tool to solve the problems of cultural and creative industry enterprises. A more extended period is needed to conduct further research to verify the findings and further test the results.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTITIONERS AND RESEARCHERS

A. Recommendation for practitioners

Enough activities and training courses are insufficient to support the company's employees. Team development should do more to help employees develop and realize their own value and provide avenues for employees' career development and skill enhancement. To offer more support for the development of corporate employees, There can be more opportunities to participate in exhibitions, attend academic organizations and participate in various training. These changes can help employees achieve their sense of identity, have the corresponding social status and organizational recognition, and institutionalize these contents and methods. The organization can also accomplish more of its own identity. Subsequently, the commitment to the organization can be improved constantly. In the researcher's opinion, the more practice team development, the more influence it has on team members. Therefore, an extended period will help them experience more systematic thinking about behaviors and methods. Coaching, including team building, should continue for another six months. The researcher can continue to serve as a coach. A coach's value will help guide and support team leaders in reflection, learning, and practice. It will also help to reinforce and thus change or transform their behavior. This approach should contribute to the organization's employees' innovative performance and organizational engagement and result in sustainable behavior change.

In addition to team building, there is a need to enhance the open-mindedness of the organization's members. This should be done by providing systematic thinking practice on the same topics while adding more examples of behavior and sharing experiences with each other. They can communicate and reflect more to improve collaboration and communication with each other, which will boost team performance. Group meetings can be conducted to summarize and share ideas and continually stimulate new inspiration.

Leaders can give employees more autonomy in their work to improve innovation performance, work autonomously within the scope of their responsibilities, and listen to their suggestions. In this way, employees can understand and analyze their proposals from different perspectives of systematic thinking, select better recommendations with an open mind, and put the good ones

into practice. Trust and empowerment of employees can also further strengthen employees' sense of identity and open-mindedness and further promote innovation performance and organizational engagement levels.

B. Recommendations for researchers

Based on the theoretical framework can find some gaps in the research.

First, the similarities and differences between individual and organizational mental models should be explored from the theory of mental models. There are differences between individual and organizational mental models, and the association between them needs further research to explore the management and mutual influence between organizational learning and individual learning.

Second, from social identity theory, the influence of social identity on organizational citizenship behavior should be studied. The influence of identity on innovation performance and employee engagement is described in this study. The next step can be to investigate further identity's influence on organizational citizenship behavior, which affects organizational performance.

Third, the correlation between employee involvement in organizational goal-setting and innovation performance should be studied from the goal-setting theory. The relationship between employees' goal setting for the organization can increase organizational involvement, and organizational innovation performance can be further investigated.

Finally, the researcher found that the R-squared value of ordered logistic regression testing the hypothesis is not very high. Further research can continue to analyze the reasons, find more influencing factors, and do more in-depth analysis on this issue.

C. Limitation of the study

This paper has certain limitations—first, the limitation of the study's sample size. The sample size is from a cultural and creative enterprise in China. Future studies should include data from other references for the universality of research results. Second, the ODI process is in the covid-19 time. The data are collected within a limited time. Some intervention practices had been affected to some extent by the epidemic and could not develop fully. Because of the changes in the external environment and corporate strategies, the development of innovation performance can be discussed in conjunction with the stage and direction of organizational learning during longitudinal research.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Creative Industries Innovation Center. (2013, December): *Valuing Australia's Creative Industries Final Report*. www.creativeinnovation.net.au.
- [2.] Smith, Hon Chris, et al., (1998). *Creative Industries Mapping Documents, Background*. <http://www.culture.gov.au/NR/rdonlyres/338EFCBC-F706-4191-A1A4-CCB7EFF7EDA/0/foreword.pdf>.
- [3.] Senge, P. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday.
- [4.] Reese, S. (2020). Reflecting on impacts of Peter Senge's Fifth Discipline on learning organizations. *The Learning Organization*, 27(1), 75-80.
- [5.] Checkland, P., & Poulter, J. (2006). *Learning for action: a short definition account of soft systems methodology and its use for practitioners, teachers, and students*. UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- [6.] Flood, R. L. . (2001). Local systemic intervention. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 128(2), 245-257.
- [7.] Yeager, D. S., Carroll, J. M., Buontempo, J., Cimpian, A., & Dweck, C. S. . Teacher mindsets help explain where a growth-mindset intervention does and doesn't work. *Psychological science*, 33(1), 18-32.
- [8.] Glynn, M. A. (1996). *Innovative genius: A framework for relating individual and organizational intelligence to innovation*. *Academy of management review*, 21(4), 1081-1111.
- [9.] Verducci, S. (2017). Dramatic Openings: A Role for Make-Believe in Open-Mindedness. *Philosophy of Education Archive*, 219-228.
- [10.] Madison, B.J. (2017). Is open-mindedness truth-conducive? *Synthese*, 196, 2075-2087.
- [11.] Song, Y. (2018). The moral virtue of open-mindedness. *Canadian Journal of Philosophy*, 48, 65 – 84.
- [12.] Sheikh, F.M. (2022). Open-Mindedness and the Companions of the Cave: Qur'an and the Temporal Elaboration of Muslim Subjectivity. *Islam and Christian-Muslim Relations*, 33, 167 – 190.
- [13.] Lambie, J.A. (2014). Previous Approaches to Open-Mindedness: From Socrates to the Present.
- [14.] Hogg, M.A. (2016). Social Identity Theory.
- [15.] Spears, R. (2011). Group Identities: The Social Identity Perspective.
- [16.] Hogg, M.A. (2021). Self-uncertainty and group identification: Consequences for social identity, group behavior, intergroup relations, and society. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*.
- [17.] Hogg, M.A., van Knippenberg, D., & Rast, D.E. (2012). The social identity theory of leadership: Theoretical origins, research findings, and conceptual developments. *European Review of Social Psychology*, 23, 258 - 304.
- [18.] Sikharulidze, D.I., & Kikutadze, V. (2017). Innovation and Export Competitiveness: Evidence from Georgia Firms. *European Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 8, 131-137.

- [19.] Tuhin, R. (2016). Modeling the relationship between innovation and exporting: Evidence from Australian SMEs.
- [20.] Niu, P., Xie, F., & Leonard, T. (2010). Empirical study of the relations between the knowledge base and innovation performance of an economy. *Journal of Knowledge-based Innovation in China*, 2, 171-185.
- [21.] Samambayeva, A., & Fernández-Grela, M. (2013). The Internal Innovation Processes in Kazakhstan.
- [22.] Kahn, W. A. (1992). To be fully there: Psychological presence at work. *Human relations*, 45(4), 321-349.
- [23.] Albrecht, S., Breidahl, E., & Marty, A. (2018). Organizational resources, organizational engagement climate, and employee engagement. *Career Development International*, 23(1), 67-85.
- [24.] Ali, Z., Sabir, S., & Mehreen, A. (2019). Predicting engagement and performance through firm's internal factors: Evidence from textile sector. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 16 (5), 763-780.
- [25.] Harter, J. K., Schmidt, F. L., & Hayes, T. L. (2002). Business-unit-level relationship between employee satisfaction, employee engagement, and business outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Journal of applied psychology*, 87(2), 268-279.
- [26.] Khoreva, V., & van Zalk, M. (2016). Antecedents of work engagement among high potential employees. *Career Development International*, 21(5), 459-476.
- [27.] Kamboj, S., & Sarmah, B. (2022). Antecedents and Consequences of Employee Engagement for a Diverse Workforce. *Research Anthology on Changing Dynamics of Diversity and Safety in the Workforce*.
- [28.] Shrotriyia, V.K., & Dhanda, U. (2020). Development of employee engagement measure: experiences from best companies to work for in India. *Measuring Business Excellence*.
- [29.] Shantz, A., Alfes, K., & Latham, G.P. (2016). The Buffering Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on the Relationship Between Work Engagement and Behavioral Outcomes. *Human Resource Management*, 55, 25-38.
- [30.] Nawrin, R. (2018). Mediating role of meaningful work between resources and work engagement in Bangladesh's private banks. *Management & Marketing*, 13, 777 - 795.
- [31.] Senge, P. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday.
- [32.] Senge, P. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday.
- [33.] Tjosvold, D., Morishima, M., & Belsheim, J. A. (1999). Complaint handling on the shop floor: Cooperative relationships and open-minded strategies. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 10(1), 45-68.
- [34.] Simon, B., Loewy, M., Stürmer, S., Weber, U., Freytag, P., Habig, C., ... & Spahlinger, P. (1998). Collective identification and social movement participation. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 74(3), 646-658.
- [35.] Prajogo, D. I., & Ahmed, P. K. (2006). Relationships between innovation stimulus, innovation capacity, and innovation performance. *R&D Management*, 36(5), 499-515.
- [36.] Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness studies*, 3(1), 71-92.
- [37.] Ackoff, R. (2010). *Systems thinking for curious manager*. London, England: Triarchy Press.
- [38.] Senge, P. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization*. New York: Currency Doubleday.
- [39.] Hammond, D. (2002). Exploring the genealogy of systems thinking. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 19(5), 429-439.